

ISic0475

Fragment of a base

Language

Latin

Type

unknown

Material

stone

Object

base

Editor

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Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy**Last Change**

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Agrigentum

Place of origin (modern)

Agrigento

Provenance

Seen by Mommsen in the civic museum in 1877

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Agrigento, Museo Regionale Archeologico Pietro Griffo

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

0. [---]

1. [---]S · C · QVI[---]

2. [---]MERINI[---]

Apparatus

Text of CIL

Translation

Commentary

The fragment has not been located in recent times. It is a working assumption that it was transferred into the modern museum from the original collection of the civic museum and remains to be identified in the museum stores.

Digital identifiers:

TM 491700

EDR 142397

EDCS 21900535

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7194 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650772>)

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